

fellowship to I.H. Thanks are also due to Dr. Yag Dutt, Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi for his helpful discussions and suggestion.

References

1. S. LAL, *Austral J. Chem.*, 1972, 25, 1571.
2. J. SCHUBERT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 76, 3442.
3. N. C. LI, B. E. DODDY and J. M. WHITE, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 80, 5901.
4. D. D. FERRIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 290.
5. F. KARCZYNSKI and G. S. KUPRY, *Recs. Chem.*, 1970, 44(55), 967.
6. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3397; 1954, 2904.
7. C. N. REILLEY, R. W. SCHID and F. S. SADEK, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1959, 36, 555, 619.
8. P. L. KIRK and C. L. A. SCHMIDT, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1929, 81, 237.

Synthesis of New Organotin Compounds for Protection of Crops

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Manuscript received 19 August 1974; revised 28 January 1975; accepted 24 June 1975

MEHROTRA and Dey¹ reported earlier the preparation of new organotin compounds as potential pesticidal agents. We have extended²⁻⁴ this work to incorporate fatty acids of coconut oil

and aliphatic alcohols in organotin compounds and is reported in this communication. The general steps of the reaction are as follows :

Organotin compounds from

(i) *Aliphatic acids*

(i) ALIPHATIC ACIDS

(ii) ALIPHATIC ALCOHOLS

TABLE I—PROPERTIES OF SYNTHESISED ORGANOMERCURY AND TIN COMPOUNDS

Sl. No.	Nature of R and R'	Mercury compounds		Tin compounds		Pesticidal properties of tin compounds					
		M.P. °C and yeild	Mercury percentage Found Calculated	M.P. °C yeild/ and colour	Tin percentage Found Theoretical	A.N.	C.G.	R.S.	E.C.	S.A.	
d Aliphatic acid where R											
1.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₆	206, 52	41.4 41.8	185(d), 45, Y	31.3 31.6	++	++	++	++	+	
2.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₈	200, 58	39.1 39.5	170(d), 46, F	29.2 29.4	+	+	+	++	+	
3.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₀	213, 60	37.3 37.4	168(d), 48, W	27.2 27.5	+	+	+	+	+	
4.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₂	225, 61	35.0 35.5	152, 50, W	25.4 25.8	+	+	+	+	+	
5.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₄	210, 65	33.4 33.9	177, 52, Y	24.3 24.3	+	-	+	-	-	
6.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₁₆	180, 65	32.0 32.3	205, 48, W.Y	22.6 23.0	+	+	+	-	+	
7.	CH ₃	210, 56	50.2 50.7	180(d), 46, Y	40.6 40.9	+	+	+	+	-	
8.	CH ₃ CH ₂	193, 60	48.6 49.0	170(d), 50, WG	38.6 39.0	+	+	-	-	+	
9.	CH ₃ (CH ₂) ₂	165, 54	47.0 47.3	232, 48, W.Y	37.0 37.2	+	+	+	-	-	
Aliphatic alcohols where R'											
1.	C ₃ H ₇	165, 58	50.4 50.7	152, 44, W	38.6 40.9	+	+	+	-	-	
2.	C ₄ H ₉	150, 60	48.8 49.0	185, 42, D.Y	38.5 39.0	++	++	++	-	+	
3.	C ₅ H ₁₁	195, 55	47.0 47.3	171, 41, D.G	37.0 37.2	+	+	+	-	+	
4.	C ₆ H ₁₃	186, 59	45.2 45.8	160, 43, F	35.2 35.7	++	-	-	+	-	
5.	C ₇ H ₁₅	210, 60	44.2 44.4	164, 46, G	34.0 34.2	++	++	+	++	+	
6.	C ₁₂ H ₂₅	205, 54	38.1 38.4	176, 48, Y	28.4 28.7	++	++	+	++	+	
7.	C ₁₆ H ₃₃	196, 55	34.5 34.7	156, 43, Y	24.7 25.0	+	+	+	+	+	

+ Stand for 0-50 /increased toxicity in comparison to Zineb.
 ++ Stand for 51-100/increased toxicity in comparison to Zineb.
 - Stand for 51-100/decreased toxicity in comparison to Zineb.
 Y—Yellow, F—Fawn, W—White, Y—Yellow, WY—Whitish yellow, WG—Whitish grey, DY—Dark yellow, D.G.—Dark grey, d—decomposed.

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Results and Discussions

The pesticidal properties of compounds were evaluated by method described earlier¹. The results are tabulated in Table 1.

Their fungicidal properties were best exhibited in compounds based on caprylic, lauric and myristic acids (8, 12 and 14 carbon atoms) in respect of *Chetomium globosum* and *Rhizoctonia solani* but *Aspergillus niger* was mainly inhibited by the caprate compounds. This is in consonance with the observation of Seigler and Popenoe⁴ as well as Diels and Menusan⁸, both of whom have observed maximum fungicidal and insecticidal properties in fatty acids of 10 and 12 carbon atoms found in capric and lauric acids.

In alcohol series, compounds developed on lauryl, heptyl and cetyl groups with 12, 7 and 16 carbon atom chains show greater fungitoxicity as compared to others. Individually they are most effective against *Chetomium globosum* and *Rhizoctonia solani* and *A.n.* is inhibited by compounds of lauryl alcohol. This behaviour closely supports the observation of Kears and Sijpesteijn⁹ and Zedler and Bieter¹⁰ who observed maximum activity of alkyl tin acetate associated with 9 and 12 carbon atoms.

In respect of bactericidal properties of aliphatic acids and alcohols it was observed that practically the same acid derived compounds which exhibited fungitoxic properties also show strong bactericidal character. In this respect maximum potentialities were exhibited by compounds containing 8, 10 and 12 carbon atoms. In compounds of aliphatic alcohols the bactericidal properties were mainly concentrated around those derived from 7, 12 and 16 carbon atoms.

Individually the compounds showed strong bactericidal action against *Escherichia coli* in descending order in case of caprate, carpylate, and laurate while in *Staphylococcus aureus* it was in order of laurate, caprate and caprylate. The compounds from alcohols developed on lauryl, heptyl and butyl group show better response on *Escherichia coli* and those developed on cetyl, heptyl and lauryl groups against *Staphylococcus aureus*. Strong bactericidal characters of alkyl tin compounds have also been reported by Zedler and Bieter as well as Sijpesteijn *et al.*, together with that observed by Vanderkerk and Luijten. It could be concluded that the new tin compounds based on both aliphatic acids and alcohols have a very strong potential for crop protection work.

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to the authorities of Harcourt Butler Technological Institute, Kanpur for providing facilities for the work.

References

1. G. MEHROTRA and A. N. DEY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 793.
2. G. J. M. VANDERKERK and J. G. A. LUIJTEN, *Chemia*, 1962, 14, 36.
3. H. MARTIN and F. S. SALMON, *J. Agric. Sci.*, 1931, 21, 638.

4. E. H. SIEGLER and C. H. POPENCO, *J. Econ. Entomol.*, 1925, 18, 292.
5. I. VOGEL, 'A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry', S. W. Ballantine & Co. Ltd., London, 1951, p. 364.
6. I. VOGEL, 'A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry', S. W. Ballantine & Co. Ltd., London, 1951, p. 743.
7. I. VOGEL, 'A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry', S. W. Ballantine & Co. Ltd., London, 1951, p. 641.
8. L. E. DIELS and H. MENUSAN, *Contrib., Boyce. Thonson. Institute*, 1935, 7, 63.
9. S. KEARS and SIJPESTEIJN, quoted from "Fungicides", Vol. II by D. C. Torgeson, Academic Press, N.Y., 1969, p. 338.
10. H. J. ZEDLER and C. B. BIETER, quoted from "Fungicides", Vol. II by D. C. Torgeson, Academic Press, N.Y., 1969, p. 341.

Flavones, Flavonols and Flavanones Derived from 2'-Hydroxy-4'-*n*-Butoxy Chalkones

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Manuscript received 26 December 1974; accepted 28 July 1975

BY selenium dioxide oxidation and the alkaline hydrogen peroxide oxidation, 2'-hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxychalkone gives flavone and flavonol respectively. 2'-Hydroxychalkone on cyclisation with dilute sulphuric acid or hydrochloric acid gives flavanones.

In this paper the synthesis of flavones, flavonols and flavanones from 2'-hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxychalkones¹ is described when 2'-hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxychalkone were subjected to selenium dioxide oxidation in dry *n*-amyl alcohol, 7-*n*-butoxyflavones were obtained. The chalkone dibromides¹ were refluxed with anhydrous potassium carbonate in acetone to give flavones.

The chalkones were subjected to the Algar-Flynn oxidation using alkaline hydrogen peroxide when 7-*n*-butoxy flavonols were obtained. The acetyl derivatives of flavonols were prepared using flavonol, acetic anhydride and pyridine. 2'-Hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxychalkones were cyclised to 7-*n*-butoxyflavanones using dilute sulphuric acid.

Experimental

General procedure. (a) A mixture of the 2'-hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxychalkone (1.0 g) and dry selenium dioxide (1.0 g) in dry *n*-amyl alcohol (15 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath at 130°–140° for 24 hrs. The precipitated selenium was filtered off and the filtrate steam distilled to remove the alcohol. The product remained in the flask was collected and crystallised from methanol. It is insoluble in alkali and it does not give colour with alcoholic ferric chloride. The flavones prepared are recorded in Table 1.

(b) A mixture of 2'-Hydroxy-4'-*n*-butoxy- α - β -dibromochalkone (0.5 g) and potassium carbonate (0.5 g) in acetone (25 ml) was refluxed on a water bath at 70° for 4 hr. The solution was filtered when